

IMPROVING METHODS FOR SAFE OPERATION OF HYDROTECHNICAL STRUCTURES IN COMPLEX GEOLOGICAL CONDITIONS

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This article examines measures for determining remaining resources to extend the service life of earth hydraulic structures. Currently, Class III and IV hydraulic structures constitute the majority compared to structures of other classes, and assessing their safety is one of the primary factors.

Keywords: hydraulic structures, condition, factors, service life, safety, control and measurement equipment.

Introduction: Currently, according to the Ministry of Water Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Class III and IV hydraulic structures account for 56% in the water management and hydropower sectors [1]. Most structures of this class have served up to 40-50% of their service life. Upon the expiration of the established service life, work to extend the safe service life of hydraulic structures without determining their remaining resources shall not be permitted for further operation. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the results of multifactorial scientific research in the issues of extending the service life of hydraulic structures.

Main part: In many cases, one of the main problems in ensuring the safety of Class IV hydraulic structures is the insufficient funding of safety measures. The main reason for setting a long deadline for the execution of instructions when the organization supervising the safety of hydraulic structures identifies violations and restrictions on the normal operation of hydraulic structures is related to the long process of allocating financial resources to eliminate the specified violations. Furthermore, it is natural for the operating organizations of certain hydraulic structures, which to a lesser extent cannot find a source of financing to implement the instructions of the supervising organization, to delay the implementation of measures aimed at improving the safety of hydraulic structures [2].

To achieve the set tasks for ensuring the safety of hydraulic structures, it is necessary to have a complete understanding of the technical condition and geometry of hydraulic structures. As noted above, the operation of certain hydraulic structures is carried out without project documentation. The restoration of project documentation will once again depend on funding. To achieve this, it is necessary to develop a model that describes the sequence of research work on forecasting the condition of hydraulic structures.

In statistical data, as the main factors in ensuring the safety of hydraulic structures, operating organizations noted that over the last 15-20 years, a trend has

been observed toward a decrease in the level of training for hydraulic engineering specialists within both operational services and regulatory bodies. This is because, alongside the factors affecting the safety of GTI, the qualifications of the personnel serving them also play a special role. Currently, special attention is being paid to the qualifications of hydraulic engineers in the fields of water management and hydropower, and work is being carried out in this direction [3].

The issues of ensuring the safety of hydraulic structures have been addressed by many scientists in our republic, but the works dedicated to the methodology for developing measures to extend the service life of Class III and IV soil hydraulic structures are insufficient to date, which is a necessary condition for developing such measures.

In our republic, Class III and IV soil-based hydraulic structures are widespread, most of which are low-pressure. Given that the structures are located on the territory of nearby settlements, special attention should be paid to the development of measures to extend the service life of such structures in order to protect them from the negative impact of water and create favorable economic and domestic conditions. When assessing the remaining life of the hydraulic structures, it is necessary to account for the deterioration of the physical and mechanical properties of the soils in the body and foundation of the dam [4.5].

In the construction of soil hydraulic structures, the varying distribution of soil components by volume is very characteristic, which complicates the study of their physical and mechanical properties. In most cases, the uneven distribution of components by volume is characteristic of soil-based hydraulic structures, which in turn depends on the method of construction, the quality of work performed, and the volume of construction quarries with soil material of the required quality and meeting the requirements of the construction project.

When determining the remaining operational resource, factors of environmental impact on the soil hydraulic structure and its foundation must be taken into account:

- as a result of exposure to non-aggressive, low-aggressive, and highly aggressive liquid active media, the structure will fail before the design operational period;
- wear and tear of soil construction materials under the influence of sunlight, high temperatures, and chemical and mechanical influences leads to a deterioration of the physical and mechanical properties of the soils;
- the occurrence of stress concentrations due to the periodicity of temperature and humidity leads to the destruction of the structure;
- natural disasters.

These listed types of impacts serve as the basis for the causes of failure and damage to soil hydraulic structures and their foundations. In general, the service life of earth hydraulic structures and their foundations directly depends on the wear and tear

of construction materials. The most likely causes are: mechanical and chemical suffocations; changes in the physical and mechanical properties of building materials and soils during the operation of structures and foundations; wear and tear of structural body materials and foundation soils; wave action on the structure; pore and anti-seepage pressure; drainage colmatage, etc.

From this, it can be concluded that the primary reason for considering the extension of the service life of earth hydraulic structures is the wear and tear of the hydraulic structure's body and its foundation. The wear and tear of earthen hydraulic structures is evaluated as a process of deterioration associated with the change in the properties of construction materials over time.

The process of changing the structure and properties of the building materials of earthen hydraulic structures is a form of gradual wear and tear occurring during its operation, in which it is of particular importance to determine the relationship between the causes and processes that change the properties of the body and foundation materials of the hydraulic structures.

Regular observations should be conducted to determine the remaining resource and the possibility of extending the service life of earth hydraulic structures, namely:

- assessment of the facility's compliance with the geological, hydrological, and other parameters adopted in the project;
- assessment of the strength and stability of hydraulic structures and their individual elements, taking into account the actual state of affairs;
- assessment of the discharge capacity of culverts, taking into account changes in the hydrological situation during the operation of hydraulic structures;
- assessment of the serviceability and strength of mechanical equipment and mechanisms of water supply structures;
- assessment of the exceedance of the structure crest mark above the level of accelerated settlement and, in some cases, above the level of normal settlement;
- assessment of the condition and sufficiency of the number of control and measuring apparatus.

The history of the design, construction, and operation of Class III and IV soil hydraulic structures indicates that the listed systematic observations are poorly organized or entirely absent.

In most cases, as noted above, instrumental monitoring of the condition of Class III and IV hydraulic structures is not conducted. A visual inspection of the facility is conducted by employees of the operating organization or the inspection staff of the regulatory body, which does not provide a complete assessment of the facility's condition; therefore, a detailed study of the condition of the hydraulic structures is necessary.

Conclusion: When extending the service life of hydraulic structures, it is first necessary to determine how worn out the building material of the structure is. This is

necessary for assessing the remaining resource of hydraulic structures, which requires an analysis of the wear and tear of construction materials. In short, extending the service life of hydraulic structures is based on assessing their safety and operating conditions.

References

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